

1 **An HERV-LTR associating transcript is silenced completely immediately prior to TE commitment in**
2 **human pluripotent stem cells.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of an
9 HERV-LTR associating transcript cooperating factor in lineage commitment of embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Kong, X., Li, R., Chen, M., Zheng, R., Wang, J., Sun, C. and Qu, Y., 2024. Endogenous retrovirus
13 HERVH-derived lncRNA UCA1 controls human trophoblast development. Proceedings of the National
14 Academy of Sciences, 121(12), p.e2318176121.